

An Exploration of Human Resource Management Practices in Academic Libraries

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ABSTRACT

In present days, human resources are the most vital assets for any organization, including libraries. The personnel in libraries carry out a range of important and specialized tasks to meet the goals set by their institutions. Human Resource Management is key strategic planning and implementation, significantly influencing the overall performance of the organization. Therefore, effective management and administration of human resources in libraries are crucial in the current digital, similar to other businesses and the ICT sector.

Introduction

Human Resource Management can be described as the practice of Inducting employees and looking employees within an organization commonly referred to as Human Resources, it addresses several critical areas, including compensation, managing performances, overall organizational development, health and safety, employee well-being, benefits, motivation, training, and more. HRM is instrumental in shaping workplace culture and environment while also contributing strategically to the management of personnel. It serves a crucial function in helping organizations achieve their objectives. In today's global landscape, no resource is more essential than human resources. They play a significant role in enhancing the overall capability and productivity of an organization, society, agency, country, and even the nation itself.

As a source of information, a library functions as an agency that collects, organizes, and disseminates data, impacting both the workforce and their professional training and education. Those involved in the information transfer process must possess current knowledge and skills, necessitating ongoing educational and training opportunities. The development of skills among information professionals' hinges on a combination of formal education and hands-on training in the workplace.

Human Resource Management

Human Resource Management concerned to managing employees in an organization, including recruitment, termination, training, and persuasion. Human Resource Management (HRM) involves recruiting and training new employees to maximize their potential for the benefit of the organization. Human resource management is the process by which an organization recruits and trains new employees in order to maximize their potential for the benefit of the organization. Strategic human resource management is the process of bringing in, skill development, compensation, and employee retention for the benefit of both individual employees and the organization. HR managers are responsible for identifying and implementing intelligent solutions to various employee-related issues, which have an impact on the organization's ability to improve efficiency and achieve its objectives, targets, and goals. HRM handles and manages a variety of key issues.

Role of Human Resources Management in Academic Libraries

HRM is an important part of library activities because it helps in many library activities, including:

1. Workforce operations: Establishing health and safety protocols, addressing employee concerns, and collaborating with labour unions all contribute to ensuring compliance with regulations.
2. Performance measurement: Assessing employee performance is vital, as it not only promotes individual development through constructive feedback but also guides decisions related to salary increases, promotions, and terminations.
3. Professional development: Professional growth Training programs, ranging from initial orientation to advanced courses, are designed to enhance productivity, decrease employee turnover, and lessen the need for extensive supervision.

Objectives

1. To understand the functional Human Resource Management Practices in Libraries.
2. To know the Human Resources Management practices rein context to Communication and Technology in libraries.
3. To explore the significance of the Human Resource Functional Practices in library activities.

Research Methodology

Our research is based on qualitative and secondary data, where we collected information through various journals, books, and websites to understand the role of human resource management in library activities. Through this, we observe and conduct further discussions.

Literature Review

1. Staffing Practices in the Library

S. No	Author	Year	Review
1	Kelly D. Blessinger	2005	The opportunity of library success and the continuance of a culture of knowledge sharing lies with the good and trained staff.
2	Devendra Kumar, Jamal Ahmad Siddiqui and Dr. M. M. Ansari	2010	Their study showed that Library work under non-professional staff during shifts and holidays. There is a need to

			recruit more professional staff for efficient and effective work
3	Kristina koltnerova	2012	An integral part of library planning, the core of all planning processes of the library is held by its staff. If the staff is trained and good, then planning is also good
4	MD. Milan khan	2020	The library needs good facilities, a strong collection of resources, and enough funding to provide great services to users, but the staff is the most important factor for success.
5	Torrejos et	2020	To tackle HRM challenges in libraries, suggested to develop a detailed staff handbook helpful for each position.
6	Taghram Choudhary	2020	The library needs good facilities, a strong collection of resources, and enough funding to provide great services to users, but the staff is the most important factor for success.
7	Hafijullmondal	2020	A good building, a strong collection, and a solid budget are important for a library to provide good services, but staff is the key to its success and the basis of fulfilling the library's objective.
8	De Alwis	2022	HRM practices in libraries focusing on personnel characteristics and

			classification of professionals' divisions and managerial issues
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2. Human Resource Functional Practices in Libraries

1	Arthur & Boyles	2007	HRM practices in libraries focusing on personnel characteristics and classification of professionals' divisions and managerial issues
2	Berko Arendse	2017	The strategic role of human resource functions can assist in overcoming various challenges that may arise for your organization
3	Mr. Harish Tigari	2017	To assess employee satisfaction with human resource management
4	Mr. Kumaraswamy B H	2017	Human Resource Management (HRM) in the functioning and success of library and information centres. HRM includes critical managerial functions such as planning, organizing, directing, and controlling, which are essential for the routine operations of these centres.
5	MD. Ashikumzzamana	2018	The importance of HRM cannot be overestimated as it was an important concern of library activities, including adaptability, stability, and sustainability
6	Soe	2020	HRM helps to assign the manpower in the library according to needs and

			considering an individual's skills and interests. The main task, according to 'soe', is to supply or recruit.
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3. HRM Information, Communication, and Technology Concerned Practices in the Libraries

1	Parvez Ahmad	2009	He studied important technological skills needed for library science professionals and managers.
2	Bryson	2011	He asked to manage a sustainable approach in the library through information and technological systems for fast run of data.
3	Aleksandra Bardic-Martinovic	2011	HR management is going through changes now a Technological changes are common, so adopting these changes is important for the effectiveness of work in the library.
4	T. Kavitha, Dr. S. Jeyaraman	2013	The library sector had been burst forth, and library science has has been subjected to thorough analysis for certain scope. The questionnaire offers details regarding how employers experience and respond to them employment circumstances and thereby assist the management in the establishment of robust labor relations policies.
5	Dr M Nishad Nawaz	2014	Objectives of HIRS to support the transfer, application of information on human resources or employees in the

			organization.
6	R. B. Madkholkar Mahavidyalaya	2015	It explored the HRM and emphasized that training staff at all levels in information technology is crucial for managing change and improving service quality.
7	Anjali Mary Gomes	2017	To assess the impact on sustainability to the outbreak of the pandemic in HR management.
8	Dr. Rajeshkumar M. Gamit	2018	Information and communication technology is not only a technology, but also an important part of managing library activities and data collection.
9	Wcces chronicle	2020	Library management & information communication technology were important for the fast and proper working of the library and communication system.
10	Haji Gul Wahaj	2021	Through the use of information technology in libraries, the human resource management strategy advances more quickly and improves work effectiveness comes into effect
11	Dr. J. Anand	2024	HRM, its influence on strategic leadership, and the development of library Information Systems (IS) initiatives and offerings. To attain these objectives, the researcher employed the case study method.
12	Chaudhary BhikhabhaiChelabhai		Importance of professional competencies in library and information services for

			more utilization and adaptability.
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4. Other HRM Practices in Libraries

1	Nimai Chand Saha Mrinal Kanti Das	2006	These studies highlight the importance of human interaction in digital libraries, focusing on how users interact with librarians, other users, and how librarians interact with each other
2	DR. S. Jeyaraman	2001	Upward wage increase, respecting the sentiments of the librarians
3	National University of Lesotho	2010	This shift focuses on viewing humans as a valuable resource in the workplace, rather than merely managing administrative tasks.
4	Jharia	2015	He highlighted the roles of libraries in rural development and empowerment, noting that rural libraries in India face challenges like limited collections, financial issues, and a lack of skilled staff.
5	Gamit	2018	He discussed how academic libraries contribute to developing human resources to adapt to a rapidly changing society and future advancements.
6	Imran khan	2019	In the 21 st century library environment is competitive and needs more improvement for its proper utilization.
7	Shanmugam A.P 1, Ramalakshmi, A,2, Sasthri, G 3 Baalachandran, S4	2020	The LMS (Library Management System) assists the librarians in working easily.
8	World Voices Nexus	2020	The human resources department plays a

	The WCCES Chronicle		crucial role in providing essential resources to organizations for their workforce.
9	Mohammad & Darwish	2022	The study aimed to assess how these practices affect employee productivity and the quality of services provided to library users.
10	Aktarul Islam ¹ Md. Habibur Rahman ²	2023	A literature review is important for gaining a clear understanding of a research topic and developing new ideas and theories. The researchers reviewed several related articles for this study.
11	Dr.M. Hema Sundari ,Dr.J.Kavitha Selvaranee ³ and Dr. J. Michael Mariadhas	2024	HRM challenges in libraries and suggested creating a detailed staff handbook. This guide would cover job descriptions, roles, responsibilities, relationships between positions, and tools needed for each role.
12	Dr. J. Anand	2024	HRM helps in the library to make strategic leadership and helps to achieve the objective of the library. It also helps in the growth of the library it improves the information system and services. Many researchers used the case study to know exactly about the role of HRM in the library.
13	Dr Renu thakur		No library can develop in isolation; there is a need of proper human resources.

Analysis and Discussion

The significance of human resource management in libraries and information services cannot be overstated. The primary goal of these institutions is the dissemination of knowledge, and without effective management, fostering a culture of information and knowledge sharing becomes challenging.

The advent of technology has fundamentally transformed how librarians perceive their roles and the services they provide. In the digital age, librarians serve as custodians of information, user consultants, information brokers, and lifelong learners. The modern library movement has increasingly recognized the vital contributions of library personnel on a global scale.

However, keeping pace with the rapid societal and technological advancements poses a challenge for information professionals. There is a growing awareness among these professionals regarding the types of education and training necessary for effective practice.

Recent developments in educational technology and evolving educational paradigms present significant challenges for the library and information community, particularly in adapting their information technology (IT) competencies. The revolution brought about by information technology has greatly enhanced human capabilities, impacting all facets of life. IT plays a crucial role in our daily existence, influencing speed, accessibility, confidentiality, security, and the ability to access information from virtually anywhere.

Human Resource Management (HRM) is essential for the functioning and success of library and information centers. HRM includes essential managerial activities like planning, organizing, directing, and controlling, vital for the everyday functioning of these centers.

Librarians should develop proposals for the establishment of new positions during planning periods and submit them for approval from university authorities. This will address future human resource needs and ensure that staff are trained in new technologies to achieve the library's objectives. The role of library professionals and librarians has undergone a significant transformation. It is now essential to integrate HRM and Human Resource Development (HRD) strategies both theoretically and practically at all levels of professional training. Numerous institutions in India offer short-term courses and training programs for individuals pursuing technical education in the field of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Additionally, personnel receive training through short-term courses in computer operations, website design, library automation, and networking. Many organizations in India are well-equipped with the necessary facilities and skilled personnel to provide training and develop human resources in the fields of information science and library studies, thereby addressing the challenges of contemporary times. As time progresses, various aspects evolve, making it crucial for libraries to effectively manage staff and adopt new technologies to ensure the proper functioning of library activities and to maintain the cultural relevance of library services.

Figure 1.1

Future Recommendation

The future role of Human Resource Management (HRM) in libraries will be pivotal in fostering a dynamic and adaptable workforce. As libraries increasingly embrace technology and digital resources, HRM will need to focus on recruiting and retaining skilled professionals who are proficient in both traditional library services and emerging technologies.

Some Future Recommendations for Human Resource Management in Libraries:

- Enhanced Training Programs, both traditional and digital library skills.
- Staff Development and Retention: Provide mentorships, career pathways, and support for certifications.
- Technology Integration: Make investments in user-friendly systems and promote IT education.
- Collaboration and Networking: Establish a library network for best practices by collaborating with universities.
- User-Centric Services: Train employees on engagement techniques and administer feedback surveys.
- Strategic HR Planning: Promote new roles and match personnel to library objectives.

- Diversity and Inclusion: Encourage cultural competency training and diverse hiring.

Conclusion

The significance of library and information science personnel in India has notably increased. Since the advent of the modern library movement, the value of contributions made by library staff has been steadily recognized worldwide. In the context of rapid societal and technological advancements, it has become increasingly challenging for information professionals to remain current in their knowledge and skills. These professionals are beginning to understand the types of education and training necessary for effective practice. Advances in educational technology and evolving educational methodologies present significant challenges for the library and information sector in enhancing their information technology (IT) competencies. The library environment is highly competitive, making continuous improvement essential. The management of human resources is an area within organizations that frequently changes in response to emerging technologies and their applications. Organizations can effectively identify and retain valuable human resources by assessing potential during hiring or promotion processes, creating flexible organizational structures that promote a better work-life balance for employees, and fostering intrinsic motivation among staff. The role of library professionals and librarians has undergone a substantial transformation, making it crucial to integrate human resource management and development strategies at all levels of professional training, both theoretically and practically.

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